

EFFECTS OF THREE-POINT BENDING TEST CONTROLLED
BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION ON CARBON EPOXY LAMINATES

A. FALCHI
Industrial Materials laboratory
University of Pau
Pau, 64000
FRANCE

and

J. GRACIA
Research Group of Lacq
Elf-Aquitaine Cy
Artix, 64170
FRANCE

ABSTRACT

The three-point bending test with different span-to-depth ratios has been performed on carbon epoxy laminates in order to describe their mechanical behaviour.

The AE control was used to identify in real time the successive failure modes occurring on the material .

AE results reveal that the reduction of span leads to a Tensile - Tensile/Compressive - Compressive/Shear failure mode evolution. Elf-Aquitaine company is now applying this method to control the composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

The bend test is a useful test for the evaluation of the composite materials because it displays several trends of deformation. According to the span of the supporting rollers, the test will alternately give a predominant stress, either tensile, compressive or shear stress.

A large span usually induces the flexural rupture by tensile and compressive strain. Contrary to this, a small span enhances composite shearing and delamination. The theory also describes an intermediary stage in which flexural and shear strengths intervene to generate a complex failure [1-4].

The aim of this study was to use the AE control in order to describe the experimental behaviour of carbone-epoxy laminates tested by the three-point bending test at different span ratios.

The results, checked with microscopic observation, show the AE analysis to be an efficient method for real-time identification of the main failure mode acting on composite materials.

MATERIAL AND METHODMaterial.

[16-ply] unidirectionnal laminate are made out of Torayca T300 / Narmco 5208 prepreg tape. The carbon fibre volume content is 67%, porosity 1% and density 1,6.

Sample dimensions are 120 x 10 x 2 mm.

Mechanical test.

The bend test is conducted on a 8033 Instron machine at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min.

Tests are performed at different spans ranging between 100 and 10 mm that is to say at span-to-depth ratios between 50 and 5.

Three specimens are used for each ratio. The test is driven to fracture point at the first load fall. The maximum load P measured gives the values of the flexural stress and the shear stress from the classical relationships :

$$(1) \sigma_{\max} = 3 P \Delta / 2 b e^2 \quad \text{Flexural stress}$$

$$(2) \tau_{\max} = 3 P / 4 b e \quad \text{Shear stress}$$

where Δ is the distance between the supports, b the specimen width, e the specimen thickness and Δ/e the span-to-depth ratio.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the test procedure

Acoustic emission control.

The AE equipment is a Dunegan 8000, a DE190B preamplifier of 40 dB and a DE9220 transducer with a 140 KHz resonant frequency.

The transducer is attached to the upper surface of the specimen, close to the load nose with a silicone grease.

The minimum amplitude of the AE events must be at least 30 dB to be detected. When added to the AE apparatus, a graphic recorder gives in real time the average signal level -ASL- versus the applied load (see figure 1).

The ASL measurement is the sum of the average envelop of all the pulses emitted during a constant time period of one second. The final measure is proportional to the number, the duration and the peak amplitude of the pulses generated from the material. One of

the advantages is that the measure is not dependant on the threshold detection.

ASL measurement is an energy measurement which represents the global AE activity of a material subjected to irreversible damage.

A previous study has shown that ASL increase begins with the onset of first ruptures and its development occurs in relation to the amount of damage [6].

RESULTS

Mechanical results.

The mechanical behaviour of carbon epoxy laminates agrees with the theory except that there is a continuous increase rather than the shear stress hold normally predicted (see figures 2 and 3). The span-to- depth ratio directly influences the stress distribution. Therefore AE control and microscopic observation were used to complete the mechanical evaluation which can not describe the experimental failure mode transition.

Figure 2. Analytical stress distribution for carbon-epoxy laminates

Figure 3 . Experimental stress distribution for carbon-epoxy laminates

AE results.

The most significant AE responses plotted in figure 4 indicates the following three behaviours which also coincide with microscopic observations:

(a) $50 \ll \Delta/e \ll 25$ and $\Delta ASL \ll 4$ dB : Progressive growth of the AE activity until the specimen fails. Although this is a brittle rupture, AE response is not dynamic because ASL intensity remains lower than 4 dB. Microscopic observation of the edge of the sample, under the load nose, revealed broken fibres only in the lowest plies which had been submitted to tensile stress (see figure 5).

(b) $20 \ll \Delta/e \ll 15$ and $\Delta ASL \ll 8$ dB : Development of a complex failure.

After the progressive degradation of (a) there followed a significant increase in ASL intensity close to the rupture.

Microscopic observation not only shows the fibre-breakage in the tensile region but also the fibre-buckling in a transverse fault due to compressive stress in the upper region.

When the span-to-depth ratio decreases, the transverse fault which was first confined to the highest plies then deepens toward the center of the specimen.

(c) $12.5 < \Delta/e < 5$ and $\Delta ASL > 8$ dB : A delayed initiation of AE activity close to the maximum load.

The ASL intensity immediately reaches the maximum value of degradation (b) and then increases until the fracture occurs. Additionally, at the lowest span-to-depth ratios, the ASL could further increase after the failure.

Microscopic observation reveals how the compressive region develops with the increase of the transverse fault with a following delamination in the longitudinal direction. No tensile rupture in the low plies can be observed.

The correlation between AE results and microscopic observations provide the schematic illustration of the main failure modes which is plotted in figure 5.

Figure 4. AE real-time responses recorded for carbon-epoxy laminates at different span-to-depth ratios.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. Microscopic observations of the 3 main failure modes occurring on carbon-epoxy laminates subjected to bend tests.

DISCUSSION

At each span, the AE control differentiates the main failure modes and their real-time evolution. The development of AE activity from series (a)-(b)-(c) corresponds to the Tensile - Tensile/compressive - Compressive/Shear failure mode evolution. This can be illustrated in figure 6 which represents ASL intensity vs the percentage of maximum load : Specimens (a) tested at wide spans fail in tensile mode from 60% of maximum load onwards. Specimens (b) tested at intermediate spans show a mixed mode where compressive rupture occurs after the tensile rupture. Specimens (c) tested at narrow spans develop a compressive/shear mixed mode leading to delamination.

Figure 6. Failure mode identification with AE Control.

The AE results bring forth concepts which complete the mechanical theory of carbon epoxy laminates subjected to bend test.

. Tensile concept. Compared with interfacial rupture and delamination, tensile rupture releases little energy. This means that fibre breakage and small matrix cracks characteristic of tensile mode only generate low amplitude and short duration pulses.

. Chronological concept. Test at wide span results in the tensile rupture of the fibres without compressive failure of the specimen. However, compressive mode is associated with a complex failure which results in the breakdown of the fibre-matrix interface. Therefore, flexural testing giving a compressive rupture prior to tensile rupture indicates a premature decohesion between fibre and matrix. This can be used as a quality criterion to control fabrication processes or to compare different products.

. Delamination concept. Because AE response always indicates compressive failure prior to delamination we conclude delamination mode to be a result of the compressive/shear mixed mode. The beam subjected to longitudinal shrinkage begins to respond with fibre buckling and breakdown of the interfacial bond. A transverse fault divides the beam into two blocks which slide underneath each other along the fault plane. This vertical shift induces the horizontal shear stress leading to delamination.

CONCLUSION

According to the spacing of the supports, the bend test is useful for the estimation either of the quality of the fibre or the interface condition for composite materials.

The advantage of the test is that the specimens do not require tab protection to prevent local crushing and background noise which usually occur with tensile machines. In this case, bend tests monitored by AE are considered highly desirable in the characterization procedure.

As a conclusion we plotted in figure 7 all the main failure modes identified by AE analysis. The diagram also involves results

previously obtained in various tests and various stacking sequences of carbone-epoxy laminates designed by the Elf-Aquitaine Co. [6]. This endorses the fact that the fibre-matrix interface is the weakest point of composites but one of the easiest mode to be detected by AE control.

Figure 7. Main failure modes identified with AE analysis for various tests and stacking sequences on carbon-epoxy laminates.

REFERENCES

1. Whitney, J.M., Daniel, I.M. and Pipes, R.B., Experimental Mechanics of Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials, Society for Experimental Stress Analysis Publishers, Connecticut, 1982.
2. Rosen Saft, M. and Marom, G., Evaluation of bending test method for composite materials, J. Comp. Tech. and Research, 16-1, pp.12-16, 1985.
3. Whitney, J.M. and Browning, C.E., On short-beam shear test for composite materials, Experimental Mechanics, 25-3, 1985, pp. 294-300.
4. Shih, G.C. and Ebert, L.J., Flexural failure mechanisms and global stress plane for unidirectional composites subjected to four-point bending tests, Composites, 17-4, 1986, pp. 309-320.
5. Sato, N. and Kurauchi, T., Fracture mechanism of unidirectional carbon-fibre reinforced epoxy resin composite. J. Mater. Sci., 1986, 21, pp. 1005-1010.
6. Falchi, A.J.M., The average signal level monitored with an AE equipment: A possible damage criterion for composite materials, 2nd Intern. Symp. on AE and Composite Materials, Montreal, 1986.